

Assessing the Effects of Cultural Norms on Gender Inequality in Brazil

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Abstract: This study analyzes the cultural effects on children and adolescents (CAs) demand for fetching water activities and their impacts on gender inequality in education in terms of CAs' school dropout probability (SDP). Adopting a probit specification, we found that, due to adverse weather events, school girls are less (more) likely to drop out of school in the matrilineal (patrilineal) kinship society than school boys. Additional years of schooling and improved health status negatively affect CAs' SDP and reduce the gender gap in education. These effects are statistically significant at conventional levels, either controlling for local and household-specific effects or affected versus unaffected areas by drought, suggesting that culture matters for gender outcomes.

Keywords: Kinship traditions; Gender gap in education; Economic development

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1. Introduction

One of the hot topics in the economic development literature concerns women's and men's decisions regarding resource allocation within a household (e.g., D'Exelle and Ignowski, 2022). Presumably, who controls resources is an important matter because it signals the role and sphere of influence of everyone (Armand, et al., 2020). For instance, a woman with decision power may invest more in children's development, contributing to reducing gender inequality traps (Duflo, 2012). However, what is the role of culture on gender outcomes is not well documented. Yet, the culture may perpetuate gender inequality in several of its dimensions: the cultural norms dictate the social division of tasks. This culturally intra-household labor division can be a primary source of gender inequality in education. For instance, when the household faces a weather shock such as drought, water scarcity increases the labor unit requirement. Because of boys' preference values predominance (e.g., Marco-Gracia and Tapia, 2020), girls may spend more hours searching for water for household consumption, increasing the school dropout rate for girls.

Building on a nascent economic-anthropological literature on the role of culture in gender outcomes (Bau, 2021), this study aims to provide micro-level evidence on how kinship

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tradition system affects household response to the weather shocks favoring male education in Brazil. Specifically, we analyze the effects of rainfall deviations on children and adolescents (CAs) demand for fetching water activities, measured by worked hours, as the main channel of gender inequality in education, in terms of CAs' male and female school dropout probability (SDP).

Brazil is an ideal scenario to test the cultural hypothesis. This country encompasses a significant part of the Amazon Forest, where weather shocks occur with higher frequency. Gender inequality in education has risen substantially in favor of boys (from 18.4% in 2000 to 30.7% in 2016), but the causes of this outcome are still not well analyzed. Relatively rare evidence exists for other regions (e.g., Shah and Steinberg, 2017). The focus on CAs is of particular interest because it can redirect early interventions to mitigate climate challenges.

We model the school dropout decision by the married couple and then use a two-step dynamic probit specification to estimate CAs' SDP. The key finding is that, due to adverse weather shocks, schoolgirls are about 0.2189 percentage points less likely to drop out of school in the matrilineal setting than schoolboys, suggesting that culture matters. The remainder of this study is structured as follows: Sections 2 and 3 present the theoretical framework and empirical strategy, respectively. Section 4 discusses the results. Section 5 concludes.

2. Conceptual framework

We build on Bago and Dessy (2020).The setup is the following: there is onemulti-person household indexed as $i \in [0,1]$.The fundamentals of the couple primitivity in each household are contained in the vector $Z_i = [E_i, B_i, K^i_6, G_i]$, where E_i is the level of education, B_i is the health status, K^i_6 is the 6-18 years old CAs, and G_i is other relevant factor such as married status (M_i)and occupational profile $A_i \in [0,1]$ at parent' setting (S_i).

Assumption 1: Kinship system creates asymmetry in the couple's occupational choice $A_i \in [0,1]$.

Let ω_i denote labor marginal productivity by gender, represented as:

$$w_i = \theta_i F_{Li}(T, L_i, r) \tag{1}$$

where θ_i is a parameter measuring the gender heterogeneity in A_i ; T is the quantity of land, L_i is the labor demand, and r is the rainfall. The partial derivative of functions (1) gives the following effect of weather shock on equilibrium wage:

$$\frac{dW^*_{L_i}}{dr} = \theta_i \frac{dF_{L_i}}{dr} \tag{2}$$

At equilibrium level, wage is equal to labor productivity, so that rainfall deviation affecting labor productivity may impact household's total income. In the patrilineal society, weather shocks such as drought increase the couple's female CAs' SDP¹, which should decrease whereby it is a matrilineal setting. Each household performs a multi-stage decision to maximize a convex utility function (u_i) with respect to a consumption of public good (X_i) and (couple) specific consumption goods ($\ln N_i$).

$$u_i = +\delta \ln X_i + \tau \ln N_i \tag{3}$$

where $\delta = 0$ is an indicator function equal to 1 if, and only if, $K^i_6 > 0$. N_i may indicate some level of pleasure or satisfaction attained by the household from belonging to a specific kinship tradition that makes the couple feels at least as good as in their pre-marriage living conditions (i.e., when $\tau = 0$). The public good, X_i , has a Cobb-Douglas functional form, and depends on the quantity (K^i_6) and the level of cognitive development attained by CAs (Bago and Dessy, 2020).

Assumption 2: There is a non-linear but positive relationship between the couple's level of education and CAs quality.

A couple with a higher education level is expected to increase the cognitive development of the CAs and encourage their schooling attendance. The individual' objective is to maximize Eq (3) subjects to the budget constraint:

$$y_i A_i \theta_i P_c K^i_6 S_i B_i = \vartheta_i M_i + R_i G_i \tag{4}$$

where ϑ_i is the couple permanent income.

3. Empirical Strategy and data

We adopted a two-step corrected procedure for endogeneity bias starting with the following probit specification:

$$\text{sdp}^{*g}_{i0} = \mathbf{z}_{it} \boldsymbol{\varphi} + \gamma \mu_i + n_{it} \tag{5}$$

and estimate:

$$E(\mu_i | \text{sdp}^{*g}_{i0}) = E(\mu_i | \gamma \mu_i + n_{it} \geq -\mathbf{z}_{it} \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \tag{6}$$

Next, we estimate

$$\text{sdp}^{*g}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \mathbf{x}_{it} \boldsymbol{\beta} + \delta \text{sdp}^g_{i,t-1} + \sigma E(\mu_i | \text{sdp}^{*g}_{i0}) + \gamma_i + \mu_i^* + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{7}$$

The intercept is omitted in (5) and (6) for simplicity; The dependent variable, sdp^g_{it} ($\text{sdp}^g_{i,t-1}$) is now an index equals to one (when $\text{sdp}^{*g}_{i0} \geq 0$) if school child i living in local kinship society i drops out of school in year $t(t-1)$ and never return, and

¹Note that $0 < \theta_i < 1$.

zero otherwise; x_{it} or z_{it} is the control variables for time varying individual demographic characteristics (E_i and H_i); γ_i is the individual specific effects controlling for time unvarying components (M_i and S_i); and $\mu_i, n_{it}, \varepsilon_{it}$ are the error terms.

Weather data is total daily precipitation (in millimeters) from 2000 to 2015. These data were obtained from the National Institute of Space Research (INPE). We compile this database with data from the School Census of the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research (INEP), rounds 2007, 2010, and 2012, the National Health Survey (PNS), 2013 and 2019, and the Continuous Household Sample Survey (PNAD), rounds 2007, 2010, and 2012, released by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE). The descriptive statistics of the model variables are presented in the appendix (Table A).

4. Results and Discussions

This section presents the results of the estimated model (Table 1). Adverse weather shocks have contemporary and past positive effects on CAs' SDP. Schoolboys are more (less) likely to drop out of school in the patrilineal (matrilineal) kinship system due to adverse weather events. Conversely, schoolgirls drop out of school less(more) in the matrilineal (patrilineal) society. These partial effects are statistically significant at conventional levels. This result suggests that a couple may respond an income shock retaining female labor for mitigation in the patrilineal kinship society the most.

Table 1: School dropout probability by kinship system

Variable	Patrilineal kinship		Matrilineal kinship	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
Raint	0.0086 ^{***}	0.1474 ^{***}	0.2615 ^{***}	0.0426 ^{**}
Raint-1	0.0366 ^{***}	0.2243 ^{***}	0.3456 ^{***}	0.0127 ^{***}
Incomet	-0.0676 ^{***}	-0.0313	-0.0616 ^{***}	-0.1580 ^{***}
Incomet2	-0.01614 ^{***}	-0.0124 ^{***}	-0.0133 ^{***}	-0.0190 ^{***}
Education	-0.0601 ^{**}	-0.01569 ^{***}	-0.0223 ^{**}	-0.1477 ^{***}
Health	-0.3456 ^{***}	0.0937 ^{***}	-0.0094 ^{***}	-0.2615 ^{***}
School dropout in t-1	0.0712 ^{***}	0.0232	0.0548 ^{***}	0.1310 ^{**}
Private	-0.2133 ^{***}	-0.1117 [*]	-0.2133 ^{***}	-0.6943 ^{**}
Constant	0.7144 ^{****}	0.5428 ^{****}	0.56733 ^{***}	0.5945 ^{***}
Observations	151,490	170,940	122,430	365,994
Prob > chi2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Note: * p <0: 10, ** p <0: 05, *** and p <0: 01.

However, positive variation in relatives' income (or improved health) contributes to lowering the CAs' SDP in both settings, although the effects are more pronounced in the

matrilineal society. These outcomes imply that the income increase may reduce the need for parents to withdraw their CAs from schools. Likewise, additional year of schooling of relatives causes a decrease in schoolboys (school girls)' SDP the most in patrilineal (matrilineal) kinship tradition, reflecting the effect of the return to education on gender outcomes. We also find that CAs are less likely to drop out of school when the school is under private rather than public administration. THIS result may suggest, for example, that violence against girls is lower in public schools for a given social setting, so school girls' SDP is lower in private schools for school-age students considered.

These results are robust and consistent with past work by Ashraf et al. (2016). They found evidence that educational attainment is higher across bride price groups (i.e., in patrilineal kinship system) relative to non-bride price groups (i.e., in matrilineal kinship system) in Indonesia and Zambia. Our findings have several political implications. Although the Millennium Development Goals have emphasized the role of gender equality for sustainable development, in Brazil, the discussion regarding to this subject seems to ignore the influence of culture in shaping important household decisions affecting gender outcomes. This study can be vital in designing measures to mitigate weather shocks impacts on girls in this country.

5. Conclusions

This study uses household surveys and weather data to analyze the significance of the kinship tradition system on the gender gap in education in terms of schoolboys' and schoolgirls' SDP in Brazil. We found that adverse weather shocks impact CAs' SDP according to their parents' kinship setting. The debate on gender economic outcomes in developing countries must consider cultural norms. That is important to find a potential policy to guide the resource allocation to reduce gender inequality traps in culturally heterogeneous societies.

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Appendix -Table A: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Observations	Mean	Std. Deviation	Min	Max.
Dropout	3,239,988	0.3868	0.487	0	1
Weekly income	484,367	1150.386	1757.351	0	32500
Rainfall	739,429	179.903	293.840	0	4095
Tradition	516,109	1.014	0.353	0	2
Years of education	452,692	10.846	4.127	0	16
Health status	484,928	2.188	0.755	1	5

Source: Household Surveys (HS).